

Web Style Guide

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Guidelines

Why Use Guidelines?

Style guidelines are a set of rules and guides that designers follow when putting a brand's identity out into the world. If any of these are altered or distorted, they no longer represents the brand the way it was designed to.

Who is this Guide For?

This guide may be used by anyone who is producing visual assets, both internally and externally. It may be useful to share with staff members so they can gain familiarity and understanding of the visual brand.

It is important to share this guide with anyone who will be producing any visual assets for the brand.

- 1 It is a toolkit**
Style guidelines provide the necessary tools and information to ensure all visual applications of a brand are consistent.
- 2 It maintains consistency**
Maintaining a consistent style will ensure the brand remains recognisable and professional across all means of communication.
- 3 It ensures quality control**
Visual work must meet the standards set within the guidelines. Everyone working with the brand understands what is expected and required when producing assets.

Who We Are

The OA Journals Toolkit is an online resource providing helpful articles and other information to support the development of scholarly journals of all sizes, disciplines and languages. It will provide its users with the tools they need to set up, launch, and run an academic journal, according to globally recognised standards and best practices.

The Toolkit will represent the diversity of the global scholarly community and the resources included in the Toolkit should reflect the range of stakeholders that can benefit from it such as publishers, editors, authors, technical providers, researchers, librarians, and others.

Our Values

Purpose

The OA Journals Toolkit is a community-led initiative designed to provide support for a diverse community of users across all stages of the journal development lifecycle.

Principles

- ▶ To enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs
- ▶ To provide members of the scholarly publishing community with a toolkit of relevant and accessible resources that will enable open access publishing using best practices and standards
- ▶ Recognising and supporting the diversity of disciplines, geographies and languages in scholarly publishing

Promise

- ▶ Users will gain awareness of relevant resources and knowledge to help develop and manage an OA journal
- ▶ The OA Journal Toolkit will be a starting point and step by step guide to journal development and management from an up-to-date, impartial and trustworthy source
- ▶ Users will be a part of an evolving community and that they can learn from others and share knowledge with others

Audience

- ▶ 25 - 39
- ▶ Global
- ▶ Publishers, editors, authors, technical providers, reviewers, researchers, and librarians

Colours

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Overview

All colours in the palette will be provided in RGB format. This is to be used for digital application only.

It is important to use the correct colour values for the corresponding application. If an RGB colour value is used for print, for example, the printed colour may look completely different. Please contact your designer if you would like matched colour conversion values and assets.

RGB is for Screen

Red, Green and Blue make up all of the colours you see on a digital screen. A digital device creates any colour by mixing red, green and blue and varying their intensity. This is known as additive mixing. All colours begin as black darkness and then red, green and blue light is added on top of each other to brighten it and create the perfect pigment.

When red, green and blue light is mixed together at equal intensity, they create pure white.

Core Palette

These are the colours for OA Journals Toolkit. Please do not use any other colours that fall outside of this palette.

Navy

R0 G10 B46
#000A2E

Petrol Blue

R0 G64 B87
#004057

Emerald

R0 G102 B102
#006666

Yellow

R255 G181 B23
#FFB517

Sky Blue

R112 G219 B232
#70DBE8

Bottle Green

R0 G71 B71
#004747

Forest Green

R0 G47 B47
#002F2F

Mint

R224 G255 B250
#E0FFFA

Accessibility Guidance

All text should have a sufficient contrast ratio to meet accessibility requirements. Please only use the following combinations of foreground/background colours for text to comply with this.

**Navy
Mint**

**Navy
Yellow**

**Forest Green
Yellow**

**Emerald
Mint**

**Bottle Green
Mint**

**Forest Green
Mint**

Accessibility Guidance

All text should have a sufficient contrast ratio to meet accessibility requirements. Please only use the following combinations of foreground/background colours for text to comply with this.

**Petrol Blue
Mint**

**Navy
Sky Blue**

**Forest Green
Sky Blue**

Logo

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Dark Logo

The logo is responsive to adapt to different-sized applications. These versions of the logo may be used against light-coloured backgrounds.

Landscape Logo

Portrait Logo

Icon

Light Logo

The logo is responsive to adapt to different-sized applications. These versions of the logo may be used against dark-coloured backgrounds.

Landscape Logo

Portrait Logo

Icon

Exclusion Zone

The logo must always be placed within its exclusion zone boundaries.

Always allow a minimum boundary space of the height of 'O' around all iterations of the logo.

Logo Rules

It is important the use of the logo remains consistent. The logo should not be misinterpreted, modified, or added to. Its orientation, colour, and composition should remain as indicated in this document - there are no exceptions

Do not
Stretch, distort or rotate the logo.

Do not
Add drop shadows or effects.

Do not
Add 3D or bevel effects.

Do not
Place text/images that encroach on the logo's spacing, or overlap with any other graphical elements.

Do not
Outline the logo.

Do not
Alter the colours or add any additional text.

Typography

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Heading Font

Golos Text Bold & SemiBold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn
OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()_+="':?><

Body Font

Golos Text Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn
OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()_+="':?><

Typography System

Golos Text Bold

Heading 1

Golos Text Bold

Heading 2

Golos Text SemiBold

Heading 3

Golos Text SemiBold

Heading 4

Golos Text Regular

Body

Typography Example

Heading 2 (Golos Text Bold)

Heading 3 (Golos Text SemiBold)

Body (Golos Text Regular)

OA Journals Toolkit

Open Access

The OA Journals Toolkit is a community-led initiative designed to provide support for a diverse community of users across all stages of the journal development lifecycle.

Visual Style

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Angles

The angle of the bookmark is 35 degrees. This angle can be used to create graphic assets and cutouts. Other angles may be used for backgrounds and separators to suit the size and scale of the application.

Blockquotes

Blockquotes and testimonials are styled with the 35 degree cutout on the bottom right of the card.

OA Journals Toolkit

The OA Journals Toolkit is a community-led initiative designed to provide support for a diverse community of users across all stages of the journal development lifecycle.

35°

Bulleted Lists

Bulleted lists use the FontAwesome Right Caret icon as the bullet marker. This should be in an accessible contrasting colour to the background of the list.

FontAwesome Right Caret icon

OA Journals Toolkit

- ▶ Open access
- ▶ Scholarly publishing community
- ▶ Journal development
- ▶ A community-led initiative
- ▶ Best practices and standards

Cards

Cards can be used to highlight key pieces of information. Using any of the accessible colour combinations alongside the bookmark graphic can create a callout card.

OA Journals Toolkit

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Patterns

The pattern library consists of a variety of vector cutouts derived from the bookmark shape.

Photography

Photography should be abstract and visually dynamic. 3D renders are used to create a sense of depth, movement and intrigue to aid the visual scope of the brand. These can be coloured with a gradient map from the palette if desired. Select imagery with sufficient negative space to place text if required.

Glossary

The background features four thick, parallel diagonal lines. One line is cyan, another is light blue, one is yellow, and one is dark teal. They are arranged in a staggered pattern across the dark blue background.

Glossary

RGB

(Red, Green, Blue) colour mode is for anything that is computer-based design. This includes websites, apps, banner ad and any other design created for electronic use.

CYMK

(Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, Black) colour mode is used for print design. This includes logos, business cards, stationary, illustration, packaging and any other designs used for print.

Vector

Vector images are made up of points, lines, and curves that can be infinitely scaled without any loss in image quality.

Wordmark

A logotype refers to words or the name of a business that is designed in a special way. Examples include Pinterest, eBay, Yahoo, Coca-Cola or Google.

Logomark

A logomark is an identifying mark or symbol that doesn't contain the business name. Think of the Nike 'tick', Shell, WWF, Mercedes or Adidas for example.

Combination Mark

A combination mark is just what it sounds like – a combination of the logomark and logotype. Text and image work together to create one design, like Starbucks' or VW's logos, or a standalone combination mark, which has separate logomark and wordmark, such as Adidas or McDonald's.

Glossary

JPEG/JPG

JPEG is a lossy raster format that is one of the most widely used formats online. JPEG images have a sliding scale of compression that decreases file size tremendously, but increases artifacts or pixelation the more the image is compressed.

AI

AI is a proprietary vector image format that stands for Adobe Illustrator. The format is based on both the EPS and PDF standards developed by Adobe. AI files can be exported to both PDF and EPS files (for easy reviewing and printing), and also JPEG, PNG, GIF, TIFF and PSD (for web use and further editing).

EPS

EPS is an image format that stands for Encapsulated PostScript. Although it is used primarily as a vector format, an EPS file can include both vector and raster image data. Typically, an EPS file includes a single design element that can be used in a larger design.

PDF

PDF stands for Portable Document Format and is an image format used to display documents and graphics correctly, no matter the device, application, operating system or web browser. Because it is a near universal standard, PDF files are often the file format requested by printers to send a final design into production.

PNG

PNG is a lossless raster format that stands for Portable Network Graphics. This format has built-in transparency, but can also display higher colour depths, which translates into millions of colours.

TIFF/TIF

TIFF is a lossless raster format that stands for Tagged Image File Format. Because of its extremely high quality, the format is primarily used in photography and desktop publishing.

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